

Gimnastikaning- ta'limni rivojlantiruvchi turlari.

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Anatatsiya: Gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtiruvchi turlarida ertalabki gigienik gimnastikasi va kirishgimnastikasi shakllarida, ishlab chiqarishda va ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy madaniyat daqiqalari shaklida mashqlarni bajarish nazarda tutilgan. Bu qatorga davolash va ritmik gimnastika ham kiritilgan. Ularning asosiy maqsadi inson sog'ligini mustahkamlashdan, mehnatda uning jismoniy va aqliy ishga layoqatligini yuqori darajada saqlab turishdan iborat,

mehnat va jamoatchilik faoliyatida faolligini oshirish. : asosiy, ayollar, atletik va kasbiy-amaliy turlari.

Kalit so'zlar: asosiy, ayollar, atletik va kasbiy-amaliy turlari.

Kirish

Asosiy gimnastika sog'lomlashtirish, ta'lim va tarbiya vazifalarining yechimi uchun katta imkoniyatlarga ega. Ular mashqlarning ko'p tuzilishga egaligi va ko'p funksiyaligi hisobidan amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Bu shug'ullanuvchilarni maxsus bilimlar va ko'nikmalar tizimi bilan boyitishga, pedagogning ijodiy yondashuvi uchun cheksiz imkoniyatlarni ochib beradi. Bunday bilimlar gimnastika- bu sport-pedagogik fan haqidagi bilimlar bo'lishi mumkin: uning mazmuni, ijtimoiy ahamiyati, tarixi, uning negizida turgan mashqlar bajarilishining texnikasi va qonunlari; mashqlarni sog'lomlashtirish, ta'lim va tarbiya maqsadlarida qo'llash imkoniyatlari haqida, tanlangan o'quv, kasbiy yoki sport faoliyatiga qarab harakat va psixik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, organizmning alohida organlari va tizimlariga, ularning funksional imkoniyatlarini kuchaytirish maqsadida ta'sir qilish haqida, o'quvchilarni har tomonlama tajriba bilan boyitish, amaliy mashqlarni o'rgatish va b. Asosiy gimnastikaning mashqlari pedagog so'zi va musiqali kuzatuv bilan birgalikda samarali majmuyi vosita va shug'ullanuvchilarda shaxs fazilatlarini

tarbiyalash usuli: gimnastika mashg'ulotlariga, o'qishga, mehnat va jamoa faoliyatiga vijdonli, chuqur anglagan va faol munosabat. Jismonan va ruhan barkamol shaxsni rivojlantirish maqsadida asosiy gimnastikaning keng imkoniyatlarini qo'llash, uni barcha yoshdagi shug'ullanuvchilarning jismoniy tarbiya usuli va mustaqil vositasiga aylantirgan. O'rta yoshdagi tizimli mashg'ulotlar uzoq muddatga jismoniy va aqliy ishga layoqatligini yuqori darajada saqlab turishga ko'maklashadi. Maktabda asosiy gimnastika jismoniy tarbiya

darslariga kiritilgan, umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlik, sog'lomlashtirish guruxlarida qo'llaniladi. Mashg'ulotlarda unga kiritilgan barcha mashqlar majmui qo'llaniladi.

Ayollar gimnastikasi- ayollar organizmining xususiyatlarini va psixologik tuzilishini inobatga oladi. Mashqlarni, metodik usullarini tanlashda, eng avvalo, onalik funksiyalari inobatga olinadi, shuning uchun kuchni, tezlikni, oyoqlar, qorin va orqa tomon mushaklarining chidamliligini rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Mashg'ulotlarga umumrivojlantiruvchi gimnastik mashqlarning barchasi kiritiladi: anjomlar bilan va anjomlarsiz erkin mashqlar, gimnastik devorchada, o'tirg'ichda bajariladigan mashqlar va b. Ayollar bilan mashg'ulotlarda badiiy gimnastika mashqlari, tomosha va xalq o'yinlari elementlari va musiqa katta ahamiyatga ega. Mashg'ulotlarning musiqali kuzatuviga alohida e'tibor beriladi. Ushbu mashqlar yordamida harakatlar koordinatsiyasi, jozibasi, go'zalligi rivojlanadi, to'g'ri va chiroyli qadi-qomat shakllanadi, sog'lik mustahkamlanadi, jismoniy va aqliy ishlarga layoqatlik darajasi ko'tariladi.

Kasbiy sohaga yo'naltirilgan gimnastika quyidagi mashqlarni va metodik usullarni birlashtiradi. Ular yordamida o'z vaqtida kasbiy ta'lim boshlangancha, organizmning funksional imkoniyatlarini ko'tarish, harakatlanish va psixik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish va o'rganish (baholash), shug'ullanuvchilarga tanlangan kasbiy faoliyatiga zarur bo'lgan shaxs xususiyatlarini tarbiyalashi mumkin. Kasbiy qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishga va amaliy harakatlanish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga o'rta maxsus va oliy ta'lim muassasalarida katta e'tibor qaratilgan. Haqiqatda butun jismoniy tayyorgarlik amaliy xarakterga ega, yoxud u shug'ullanuvchilar tanlagan mehnat faoliyatini muvafaqiyatli egallash va unda kasbiy mahoratga erishish uchun zarur bo'lgan qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan.

Atletik gimnastika- mushaklar kuchini, chidamlilikni va irodani, organizmning funksional imkoniyatlarini rivojlantirish, o'smir va o'spirin o'g'il bolalarni doimiy jismoniy mashqlar mashg'ulotlariga jalb qilishning; sog'lom hayot tarzini shakllantirishning; tamaki chekish, narkotik moddalarni iste'mol qilish va sog'lik uchun zararli bo'lgan boshqa odatlarning oldini olish va shaxsni shakllantirishning; o'spirinlarni mehnatga, qiz juvonlarni onalikka tayyorlash uchun ajoyib vositasi va usuli. Atletik gimnastika gigienik gimnastikaning davomi bo'lib, sport gimnastikaning boshlanishi bo'lishi mumkin. Gimnastikanig sport turlariga quyidagilar kiradi: sport gimnastikasi, badiiy gimnastika, sport akrobatikasi va sport aerobikasi.

Sport gimnastikasi- ko'p kurashli sport turi. Uning tarkibida: erkaklarda-erkin mashqlar, ot sport anjomida, xalqalarda, bruslarda, turnikda mashqlar,

tayanch sakrashlar; ayollarda- tayanch sakrashlar, turli balandlikdagi bruslarda, gimnastik yog'ochda bajariladigan mashqlar va erkin mashqlar. Sport gimnastikasi mashg'ulotlariga badiiy va ritmik gimnastika, akrobatika, xoreografiya, o'yin va b. mashqlar kiritiladi. Sport gimnastikasi- olimpiya sport turi. Bizning davlatimizda uni Sport gimnastika federasiyasi boshqaradi.

Badiiy gimnastika- faqat ayollar sport turidir. Uning asosiy vositalari anjomlar va anjomlarsiz bajariladigan raqs xarakteriga ega mashqlar. Ular qiz bolalar va ayollar jismoniy tarbiyasining ajoyib vositasi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ushbu sport turining bir qator elementlari jismoniy madaniyat bo'yicha maktab dasturiga kiritilgan. Yuqori sinflarda badiiy gimnastika bo'yicha mustaqil mashg'ulotlar o'tkaziladi. Badiiy gimnastika- olimpiya sport turlaridan biri.

Sport akrobatikasi uch guruhdagi mashqlarni o'ziga qamrab olgan: akrobatik sakrashlar, juftlikda (erkaklar va aralash juftliklar) va gurux mashqlari. Batutda bajariladigan mashqlarni akrobatik mashqlarga kiritadilar. Akrobatik mashqlar murakkabligining keng qamrovi turli jinsdagi, yoshdagi va har xil jismoniy tayyorgarlikka ega bo'lgan shaxslarni o'rgatish imkonini beradi. Akrobatika mashg'ulotlari uchun murakkab sport jixozlari kerak emas, akrobatik yo'lakcha

va gimnastik matlar bo'lsa yetarli. Mashg'ulotlarni faqat sport zalida emas, balki sport maydonchasida ham tashkil etsa bo'ladi.

Sport aerobikasi- ushbu sport turida sportchilar murakkab koordinasion asiklik harakatlar birliklarini, turli tuzilma guruxlarning har xil murakkablikdagi elementlarni, hamda sheriklarning o'zaro harakatlanishini o'ziga qamrab olgan uzuluksiz va yuqori samarali mashqlar majmuini bajaradilar. Quyidagi mashqlar turlarini o'ziga qamrab olgan: ayollar va erkaklarning individual chiqishlari, aralash juftliklar, har qanday tarkibdagi uchliklar va oltiliklar. Ushbu mashqlarda xoreografiya asosini "tayanch" aerob qadamlari va ularning birliklari tashkil etadi.

1995 yilda Xalqaro Olimpiya qo'mitasi aerobikani rasmiy sport turi deb tan olgan va u Xalqaro gimnastika federasiyasiga kiritildi.

Foydalangan adabiyotlar

1. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi va jismoniy sifatlarning ko'chishi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 379–393. Retrieved from

2. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical education lessons in the process of umumpedagogik methods. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 345–354. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/3548>

3. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2 (1), 90–97.
4. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 90-97.
5. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi va jismoniy sifatning ko'chishi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1 (5), 379–393.
6. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Harakat malakalarini shakllantirishning fiziologik asoslari va sport texnikasini o'rgatish. *E'tiqod va madaniyatning kesishgan joylari: Amerika diniy va madaniyat tadqiqotlari jurnali (2993-2599)*, 1(9), 87-94.
7. Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). Use of Acrobatic Exercises and Their Terms In The Process of Teaching Gymnastics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1 (9), 80–86.
8. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). АЕРОБИК ГИМНАСТИКАНИНГ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 442–448. Retrieved from
9. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ ДВИЖИТЕЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ВОЗРАСТА С ПОМОЩЬЮ СПОРТИВНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА КАК ИЗ. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 457–464. Retrieved from
10. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Norms of gymnasiums and activities of gymnasiums. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 428–434. Retrieved from
11. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Methods and methods of teaching sports gymnastics in young boles. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 453–459. Retrieved from
12. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Acrobat exercise and sports gymnastika sessions through the power of development method. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 460–467. Retrieved from
13. Sirojev , S., Nuriddinov , A., & Sayfiyev, H. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. *Modern*

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Science and Research, 2(9), 187–191. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24102>

14. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). MATH MODULES IN C++ PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 834-838.

15. Jalolov, T. (2023). UNDERSTANDING THE ROLE OF ATTENTION AND CONSCIOUSNESS IN COGNITIVE PSYCHOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 839-843.

16. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). THE ROLE OF FAIR PLAY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 244–250. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24327>

17. Nuriddinov, A., Sayfiyev, H., & Sirojev, S. . (2023). WHY FOOTBALL IS THE FIRST SPORT THAT COMES TO MIND TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 200–203. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24104>

18. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). A STUDY OF THE AGGRESSIVE STATUS OF FOOTBALL FANS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 73–80. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-10>

19. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). USE OF DIGITAL SPORTS TECHNOLOGIES IN SPORTS TELEVISION. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 208–219. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-22>

20. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-25>

21. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). MANAGING THE PROCESS OF TALENT DEVELOPMENT IN SPORTS ANATASIA. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-15>

22. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS INDUSTRY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 164–182. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-18>

23. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). SOCIAL SPORTS MARKETING. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-17>

VOLUME-2, ISSUE-2

24. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). RECOVERY STRATEGY IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-18>
25. Azamat Orunbayev, (2023) NONUSHTANING MASHQ BAJARISHGA TA'SIRI. *International journal of scientific researchers* 2(2), 3-6.
26. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). USING TECHNOLOGY IN A SPORTS ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-07>
27. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). FITNES VA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA MURABBIYLIK YO'NALISHIGA KONTSEPTUAL YONDASHUV. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(8), 23–28. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/431>
28. DASTURLARI (PROGRAM). *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(7), 37–42. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/414>
29. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORT AND PHILOSOPHY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 308–317. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28042>
30. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). YEVROPA MAMLAKATLARIDA YUQORI MALAKALI FUTBOLCHI VA MURABBIYLARNI TEXNIK TAKTIK HARAKATLARINI TADBIQ QILISH METODIKASI. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 2(14), 187-189.
31. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). PHYSIOLOGICAL REACTIONS TO INTERNAL LOAD STUDY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-07>
32. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS, CULTURE AND SOCIETY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 152–163. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-17>
33. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). FOCUS ON AEROBIC (LI) TYPE OF MOTOR ACTIVITY BASED ON FITNESS PROGRAMS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 81–90.
34. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). METHODS OF ORGANIZING NON-TRADITIONAL FITNESS CLASSES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-09>
35. Yarasheva Dilnoza Ismail Qizi. (2023). TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(10), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue10-16>

VOLUME-2, ISSUE-2

36. Yarashova, D. (2023). THE IMPACT OF PLAYING SPORTS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 230–234. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24325>
37. Ярашева, Д. (2023, April). ФИТНЕС КАК ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 278-283).
38. Yarasheva, D. (2022). BOLALARDA MASHQ QILISHNING AHAMIYATI. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 19(1), 139-142.
39. Ярашева, Д. (2023). СТИЛИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ НЕТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 19(5), 6-10.
40. Yarashova, D. (2023). STRENGTH TRAINING AND STRENGTH TRAINING IN CHILDREN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 211-215.
41. Dilnoza, Y. (2024). SOG'LOMLASHTIRUVCHI MASHG'ULOTLARNING TURLARI VA SAMARADORLIGI.
42. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND WORKING METHODS OF COACHES. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 50–60.
43. Shoxrux, S. (2023). VOLLEYBOLDA OTISH TEZLIGI TUSHUNCHASI VA AHAMIYATI. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(11), 913-917.
44. Sirojev, S. (2023). THE CONCEPT AND IMPORTANCE OF SHOOTING SPEED IN VOLLEYBALL. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 187-191.
45. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORTS AND LOGIC. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 97–106.
46. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). APPLICATIONS OF SPORT PSYCHOLOGY IN THE WORLD. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 107–120.
47. Sirojev, S. (2023). TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND PHILOSOPHY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 235–243.
48. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF MUTUAL RESPECT AND KINDNESS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 215–225.
49. Sirojev, S. (2024). EFFECTS OF SOCIAL PHOBIA ON SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 318–326.
50. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). STUDYING SPORTS PSYCHOLOGY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 176–188.